

BRIDGING SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY: INSTIGATING SOLIDARITY THROUGH AN ECO-FRIENDLY PUBLIC ART

Eurydice Rayanna Lo Chan, Polytechnic University of the Philippines, Philippines,
erlchan@pup.edu.ph

ABSTRACT

Despite its pervasiveness, the concept of sustainability remains unclear. Hence, approaches tend to frame its dimensions separately. When the interaction of its dimensions influences the goals and targets established over time. Besides the environment, relationships are essential for human survival. Hence, this paper aims to provide insights into the potential of strengths-based approach in bridging the environmental and social facets of sustainability. The approach is applied to a community project in the Philippines. This resulted in an environment-friendly project and participants showing concern for the community. With this, the revelation of capabilities ensues individual inertia which is necessary for collective action to occur.

KEYWORDS

environmental; social; sustainability; strengths-based approach; community engagement

INTRODUCTION

In 1987, the United Nations Brundtland Commission defined sustainability as “meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” (United Nations, n.d.). Despite its pervasiveness and the massive popularity it has garnered over the years, the concept of sustainability still seems unclear as many people continue to ask questions about its meaning and history, as well as what it entails and implies for development theory and practice (Mensah and Casadevall, 2019). The concept of needs goes beyond simply material needs and includes values, relationships, freedom to think, act, and participate, all amounting to sustainable living, morally, and spiritually (Shah, 2008). Humans are a profoundly social species; our drive to connect with others is embedded in our biology and evolutionary history (The Greater Good Science Center University of Berkeley, California, n.d.). Therefore, being socially connected is considered a basic need as it is essential for survival (Wolpert, 2013). However, the human dimension has been neglected amidst abbreviated references to sustainability that have focused on bio-physical environmental issues, or been subsumed within a discourse that conflated ‘development’ and ‘economic growth’ (Vallance *et al.*, 2011). When it has been clear that the interaction of the dimensions of sustainability influences the goals and targets established over time. Therefore, it cannot be understood as a well-performing environmental sustainability without a balanced society, offering a decent quality of life (Pareja-Eastaway, 2012). Correspondingly, social sustainability cannot be created simply through the physical design of the community but then neither can environmental sustainability be created by physical design alone (Ricee, 2021).

As mentioned, human connection is essential in meeting the concept of sustainability. This underscores the importance of community action which is the foundation of the community development process because it encompasses deliberate and positive efforts designed to meet the general needs of all local

residents (Brennan & Berardi, 2020). However, ‘what is this action’ and ‘why one should act’ can be elusive for individuals. Communities especially in developing countries tend to define environmental practices simply as proper management of waste and resources. When responsible utilization of resources is also contingent on the successful conservation of the environment. Furthermore, it can be challenging to unify heterogeneous individuals despite belonging to the same community. The fact that humans have evolved preferences for companionship (Machalek & Martin, 2015) entails that humans do not simply connect to anyone despite wanting to be connected is innate to them. Therefore, strategies that prompt authentic interaction are much needed. This paper aims to provide insights into the potential of strengths-based approach in bridging the environmental and social facets of sustainability. Using local materials has the obvious benefit of reducing the significant environmental impacts of transporting materials long distances (Malin, 1996)). More than merely environmental, these resources can also reveal individual capabilities. This develops a sense of certainty which motivates individuals to partake in activities that benefit their community. With this, the succeeding section narrates a community project which involves diverse members of the community – bamboo craftsmen, school children, and people with disabilities. The collective action that applied the said approach resulted in environmental and social stewardship.

THE BAMBOO ART INSTALLATION OF VICTORIA

The Philippines is dominated by Roman Catholicism and has various traditions during the Christmas Season. One of the prominent symbols relevant to this special event is the Nativity Scene, which is the Belen to Filipinos. With this, a festival that incorporates a competition of different Belen-making categories was established in 2007 by the Tarlac Heritage Foundation and Commission for the Cultural Heritage of the Church (Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines, 2011). This occurs every November in Tarlac, a province in the Philippines which consists of 1 city and 17 municipalities. In Victoria, one of its municipalities, is dominated by the agricultural sector while manufacturing industries minimally operate within the locality (Municipality of Victoria Tarlac, n.d.). Therefore, public projects must be considerate of their environment and financial capacity.

Bamboos are distributed in tropical and subtropical to mild temperate regions, with the heaviest concentration and largest number of species in East and Southeast Asia (Britannica, 2022). The abundance of bamboo in the locality made it a good option as the main material for the installation. A participant suggested sourcing the bamboo poles from small villagers living in the bamboo groves. Their engagement is vital to the preservation of bamboo since they know when and how to harvest it (Schröder, n.d.). It is proven that bamboo can accommodate organically shaped structures (Nurdiah, 2015). Despite the versatility of bamboo, using the material without familiarity can result in unreliable structures. The tacit knowledge of local craftsmen is also significant for the project. They were able to easily identify which culms can be used for the formwork (Figure 1). The initial idea is for the poles to be bent using heat, but the craftsmen suggested splitting the bamboo. Split bamboo will not require heating to bend (Figure 2). This also means that lesser poles will be used.

Figure 1: Craftsmen prepare the bamboo culms harvested by small villagers residing in bamboo groves.

Figure 2: Craftsmen working on the bamboo formwork.

Small and medium enterprises of the locality are known for producing handicrafts made of water hyacinth and macramé. Water hyacinth is known as an ‘aquatic pest’ because it reduces the amount of oxygen and nutrients of the area where it is growing (Mitan, 2019). On the other side of its otherwise notorious reputation, the water hyacinth is a very good raw material for novel products that can churn in income for individuals and communities (Department of Science and Technology, Philippines, 2012). The leaves are dried and weaved into baskets and other home decor products. Macramé on the other hand is a technique of knotting textiles, such as cotton twine. Raw materials needed to produce macramé crafts are inexpensive, making it a good income source for small communities in developing countries. Hence, these prevailing industries of Victoria influenced the material choice for the nativity scene. Apparently, the enterprises employed people with disabilities. Other participants initiated to connect with these weavers, offering to assist them in assembling the wooden frames which will hold the weaved water hyacinth and macramé in place (Figure 3). A weaver suggested incorporating small crystals to glow the panels. An individual followed this with the idea of wrapping the wooden frames with junk food foil from the community waste.

Figure 3: Other community members work on various parts of the art installation.

Products (e.g. bags, clothing, etc.) made of flour sack cloth are also another means of livelihood for the localities. This biodegradable fabric was used by school children as a canvass. They were asked to create an artwork that describes what to them is the meaning of a Victorian Christmas. Twenty-six artworks, which represent each district of Victoria, were mounted to surround the nativity scene at the center (Figure 4). The impressive artworks were lit to depict the stained glass windows seen in churches. A participant suggested covering the artworks to protect it from the rain. Exhibiting these when the installation is already dismantled was also put forward.

Figure 4: Some artworks done by the school children.

By utilizing the material assets of the community, an environment-friendly art installation was produced without compromising their existing resources, which can be better allocated for permanent and long-term projects. Furthermore, project facilitation was minimal since these resources relate to their skill sets. Allowing them to lead the interaction also widened the reach of participants. The project became an opportunity for the community to see the potential when their capabilities coalesce. This resulted in events for the whole community. The first selected location for the installation is in a public park but a base must be made. An individual proposed the idea of using the municipal hall's flagpole to save time and resources. Because there was adequate space, inaugurating a Christmas market came about. An art workshop for the whole community also transpired. The artworks from the installation and the art

workshop were eventually exhibited. Several individuals voiced their appreciation on a social media page (Facebook - Taga Tarlac Ka Kung Facebook Page, 2019) “Inclusive indeed! So powerful in meaning. Story behind having this Belenismo is simply taking pride in being a Victorian”. One also said “Talents and creativity came out in this project. Nothing is impossible when we are united.” Another individual also commented that the project made him proud of being part of the community. For him, the project is simple, but the presence of the community is strongly felt. A participant spoke about being proud to be part of the project because it “redefined and raised the bar” of the festival.

Figure 5: The Bamboo Art Installation of Victoria.

CONCLUSION

This discourse has highlighted that community action is crucial in meeting the sustainability objectives. Sustainability is about satisfying human basic needs. Besides the natural resources, networks and relationships are necessary for humans to survive. However, this convoluted concept of sustainability can be difficult for average individuals to comprehend. This can hinder individual inertia which must ensue before collective action can occur. Therefore, adaptation and integration of precautionary environmental and social principles need to focus on practices that prompt authentic interactions. In this case, opportunities to demonstrate skills and talents are paramount. From an environmental perspective, benefitting from capabilities optimizes natural and economic resources. The application of such approach allows the community to experience the advantages of their collective action. Hence, it clarifies the principles of sustainability. However, it is recommended that the intervention must be reiterated in order to assess its impact on communities. It is important to note that how it translates to practice can vary depending on the community and project it will be applied. Nonetheless, there is a need to accelerate both climate action and human development. The proposed method of engagement through strengths-based approach can let communities see their role in resolving the crisis. Encouraging its practice can make sustainability become an attribute of a community. After all, ecological integrity and social well-being are altogether elements of a sustainable community.

CITATIONS

Brennan, M., & Berardi, M. K. (2020, May 18). *Importance of Local Community Action in Shaping Development*. Penn State Extension. <https://extension.psu.edu/importance-of-local-community-action-in-shaping-development>

Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia (2022, April 20). *bamboo*. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/plant/bamboo>

Department of Science and Technology, Philippines. (2012, February 16). *DOST LAUNCHES SOLUTION TO THE WATER HYACINTH PROBLEM*. DOST GOVPH. <https://www.dost.gov.ph/knowledge-resources/news/35-2012-news/238-dost-launches-solution-to-the-water-hyacinth-problem.html>

Machalek, R., & Martin, M. W. (2015). Sociobiology and Sociology: A New Synthesis. *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*, 892–898. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-08-097086-8.32010-4>

Malin, N. (1996, September 1). *On Using Local Materials*. Building Green. <https://www.buildinggreen.com/feature/using-local-materials>

Mensah, J. & Casadevall, S. R. (Reviewing editor). (2019). Sustainable development: Meaning, history, principles, pillars, and implications for human action: Literature review, *Cogent Social Sciences*, 5:1, DOI: 10.1080/23311886.2019.1653531).

Municipality of Victoria Tarlac. (n.d.). LGU Socio - Economic Profile. Victoria Tarlac. Retrieved July 23, 2021, from <http://www.victoriatarlac.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/Municipal-Profile.pdf>

Nona Merry M. Mitan, Water hyacinth: Potential and Threat, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, Volume 19, Part 4, 2019, Pages 1408-1412, ISSN 2214-7853, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2019.11.160>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214785319338453>)

Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. (2011). The President's Day: December 3, 2011. Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. Retrieved on July 23, 2021, from <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2011/12/03/the-presidents-day-december-3-2011/>

Pareja-Eastaway, M. (2012). Social Sustainability, Editor(s): Susan J. Smith, International Encyclopedia of Housing and Home, pp. 502-505, ISBN 9780080471716, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-047163-1.00571-3>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780080471631005713>)

Ricee, S. (2021, May 13). Social Sustainability – Everything You need to know. Diversity for Social Impact. Retrieved on August 08, 2021, from <https://diversity.social/social-sustainability/>.

Shah, M. (2008). Sustainable Development, Editor(s): Sven Erik Jørgensen, Brian D. Fath, Encyclopedia of Ecology, pp. 3443-3446, ISBN 9780080454054, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-008045405-4.00633-9>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780080454054006339>)

Schröder, S. (n.d.). *When and How to Harvest Bamboo*. Guadua Bamboo. <https://www.guaduabamboo.com/blog/when-and-how-to-harvest-bamboo>

Taga Tarlac Ka Kung Facebook Page. (2019, November 16). Facebook. Retrieved on July 23, 2021, from <https://www.facebook.com/tagatarlackakung/posts/2391080727872071>

The Greater Good Science Center University of Berkeley, California. (n.d.). *Social Connection Definition | What Is Social Connection*. Greater Good Science Center. https://greatergood.berkeley.edu/topic/social_connection/definition

United Nations. (n.d.). *Sustainability*. <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/sustainability>

Vallance, S., Perkins, H., & Dixon, J. (2011). What is social sustainability? A clarification of concepts, *Geoforum*, Vol. 42 No. 3, pp. 342-348, ISSN 0016-7185, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2011.01.002>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0016718511000042>)

Wolpert, S. (2013, October 10). *UCLA neuroscientist's book explains why social connection is as important as food and shelter*. UCLA Newsroom. <https://newsroom.ucla.edu/releases/we-are-hard-wired-to-be-social-248746>

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

1. All necessary data is presented in this paper.
2. Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.